

Confinement Effect on a Rectangular Reinforced Concrete Short Column with a Various Means of Confining Materials

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INTRODUCTION

This paper presents the experimental work which was carried out on a conventional rectangular short column and a confined column with a Ferro cement wall panel. The experiments were carried out on a column of size 150x230x500 mm with and without confining reinforcement and compressive load carrying capacity, failure pattern, behaviour and ductility were observed. Experimental results show that an increase in the peak load carrying capacity of the columns, improved the ductility of the columns and column behaviour is ductile type failure. The overall performance of the columns confined to the fibrocement wall panel is enhanced. The peak load value was increased by up to 70% as compared with the conventional columns. Significant decrease in the value of vertical deformation was observed.

KEYWORDS: *Confined column; ferro cement wall panel; compressive load, ductility, vertical deflection*

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INTRODUCTION

Columns are structural components that are mainly vertical spans from the substructure to the superstructure and are subjected to axial compressive load, lateral load due to earthquakes, and play a critical role in the load transfer from the top of the structure to the bottom footing. In all types of reinforced concrete constructions, columns are the most significant structural element that transfers the entire structure's load to the foundation. In 2001, the terrible earthquake in Bhuj, Gujarat, stunned the entire country. A substantial number of RCC buildings in Ahmedabad, the capital city roughly 300 kilometres from the epicentre, were either severely damaged or collapsed. After the Bhuj mishap, the severity of the provisions in IS 13920-1993 was understood by the structural consultants. The percentage of secondary reinforcement in the column ranges from 0.25% to 0.35% of the main reinforcement. IS 13920-1993's present confinement reinforcement equations do not provide a consistent level of safety against deformation and damage caused by flexural yielding during earthquakes. (According to Subramanian, 2011). The secondary reinforcement can be calculated using equation according to IS 13920-1993.

$$A_{sh} = 0.18Sh \frac{f_{ck}}{f_y} \left[\frac{A_g}{A_k} - 1.0 \right]$$

Where,

S= Pitch of spiral or spacing of hoops,

h=longer dimension of rectangular confining hoop measured to its outer face. It shall not exceed 300 mm.

Ag= Gross area of the column cross section.

Ak= Area of confine concrete core in the rectangular hoop measured to its outside dimensions.

The lack of confinement provided by ties is the driving force behind the use of materials like Expanded Metal Mesh (EMM), Welded Wire Mesh (WMM), and Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) to confine the concrete core (Ahmed 2015). When columns are subjected to significant earthquakes, transverse reinforcement in the shape of hoops, cross-ties, or spirals plays a crucial role in securing the columns. As a result, in the next iteration of the code, an equation for the design of confinement reinforcement for ductile earthquake-resistant rectangular and circular columns may be amended. The tall structure is the city's most prominent icon. Almost all of the buildings in the

smart city concept are high-rise structures that act as cantilevers vulnerable to lateral loads caused by wind and earthquakes. As a result, the column is designed to resist load and deformation in the post elastic range. It will also aid in the dissipation of energy. Structures inside the elastic range are designed for earthquakes. The column is constructed such that the elastic energy can be dispersed by post-elastic deformation of the components, which necessitates the design of specific elements for both ductility and strength.

Most codes prefer the "strong column and weak beam" paradigm to avoid the creation of plastic hinges in the column. Concrete is limited by additional transverse reinforcement to prevent the creation of the plastic hinge in the column. This will also boost the column's load carrying capacity. Rectangular columns are significant to examine since they are commonly utilised in all sorts of building construction. The failure of columns through chain action prompted the entire structure in numerous failures, according to the test results of several damaged structures. It would be unsafe to construct the structures without taking into account the possibility of plastic hinges forming in the columns. Take into account the failure of structures as a result of unforeseen events, as well as the resulting loss of lives. In order to deform laterally, transverse reinforcement in columns is required, regardless of whether it is part of a moment resistant frame or the gravity system as well as providing the requisite ductility. The following variables influence the quantity of special confinement in the column: Ratio of concrete tensile strength to tie tensile strength, the column is under axial load, the transverse reinforcement's spacing,

Longitudinal spacing and reinforcement, The ductility factor of curvature.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

To examine the compressive strength of short columns with and without special restricting reinforcement in the form of a Ferro cement wall panel.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transverse reinforcement in reinforced concrete columns provides confinement to compressed concrete, prevents premature buckling of compressed longitudinal bars and acts as shear reinforcement. The quantities of transverse reinforcement present in columns designed for seismic resistance should ensure ductile behavior during severe earthquake loading. **N Subramanian (2011 ACJ)**,It has said that the clauses of IS 13920-1993 relating to confining reinforcement should be amended since they do not take into account the following characteristics that affect the column's behaviour: 1) Constricting pressure that is effective 2) Level of axial load 3) The thickness of the unconfined cover concrete. **Paultre et. al (2008 ASCE)**,They tested 93 square and circular columns in their experiment. Simplified formulae for the design of confinement reinforcement were proposed as a result of this.

Fig. No.2 1 Stress- Strain curve for Confined and Unconfined Concrete

The graph of stress virus strains for unconfined and confined concrete is shown in Figure 1. The graph shows that confinement reinforcement can aid in improving the section's ductile behaviour. It also causes the pick to be shifted to a higher level. **Ivy et. al. (2013 ASCE)**,Nineteen full-scale circular reinforced concrete columns with a volumetric ratio of transverse reinforcement ranging from 0.23 percent to 0.918 percent were tested under axial compression. They also provided an empirical formula for forecasting peak strength. There was also mention of confinement in the form of high-performance Ferro cement.

Fig. No.2 2 Typical mode of failure of columns

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experiment was carried out on rectangular columns in order to compare the findings of the axial load carrying capability of the column without and with confining reinforcement. The effectiveness of reinforced concrete rectangular columns is less than that of circular or square columns, according to the literature review. This is due to the confinement reinforcement's inability to produce the necessary confining pressure to bind the concrete and prevent it from spalling. The column was subjected to an axial compression test in order to investigate its behaviour and failure pattern. The three sets of columns in each group are cast according to the IS 456: 2000 concrete quality acceptance standards so that the average strength and compressive strength data may be compared. The column has a fourteen-day cure period. The column's cross section is 230 x 150 mm, and its height is 550 mm. The column's cross section is 230 x 150 mm, making it ideal for testing. The column stands at a height of 550 mm. As a result, the Slenderness Ratio is expressed as

$$\lambda = \text{height of column} / \text{Least Lateral Dimension}$$

$$= 550 / 150$$

$$= 3.67 \text{ which is } > 3 \ \& \lt; 12$$

Therefore, the Column is Short Column.

Grade of concrete selected is M25
Clear cover for the column Specimen is 25 mm. 8mm ties @150mm C/C

Fig. No.3 1 Reinforcement of Columns without confining reinforcement

Fig. No.3 2 Formwork for Column

The experimental set-up is depicted in Figure 1. A Universal Testing Machine (UTM) with a capacity of 1000 kN was used to test the column (100 tones). The dial gauges are mounted on the column's four faces. This is done to acquire the column's lateral buckling in all four directions. The lateral buckling measurement is critical because if the lateral buckling rises, the concrete spalling will increase as well. The confinement that will be offered will help to decrease lateral buckling and, as a result, concrete spalling.

Fig. No.3 3 Experimental setup of Testing of Column

Observations:

Occurrence of first crack: 320 kN. Vertical deflection @320 kN: 3.4 mm. Lateral Buckling on Face D@320 kN: 0.47 mm, The Concrete used is of grade M25 which has proportion as 1:1:2. The concrete is mixed by the use of Transit Mixers. To avoid honeycombing in the concrete

continuous compaction by tamping rod is done. After two days of casting the formwork were opened and the column were kept for curing. The columns were immersed in the water tank in college laboratory for curing. The curing period is about 14 days.

Fig. No.3 4 Arrangement of Conventional Reinforcement, With Ferro cement (CRF)

CONCLUSIONS

From the above experimental work, it can be observed that the axial compressive strength of the column increased by 15% to 68% when confining reinforcement is used as compared to a column without any confining reinforcement. Column confining with Ferro cement walls is less effective than that of a column with conventional reinforcement. It is also observed that the lateral strain of the confined column reduces, resulting in a stiff and rigid column.

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